

Investigation on Possible Acid and Cation Interference in the Determination of Copper by Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy in an Air-acetylene Flame

MOSTAFA M. EMARA*, NAZIK A. FARID^{1a}, MONIR M. ALI^{1b} and ABD EL-AZIZ GHARIB

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Al-Azhar University, Nasr City, Cairo, Egypt

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The atomic absorption technique is used for copper analysis under wide experimental as well as instrumental conditions. The analysis took place in pure acidic media such as HCl, HNO₃, H₂SO₄, HClO₄ and H₃PO₄. It was found that the best acidic media for copper analysis is 2% HClO₄, using one slot burner head at 1 cm height of optimum flame. Also the effect of added cations such as Na, K, Ca, Mg and Al on the analysis of Cu was carried out in HClO₄ media. No interference was observed up to 10000 ppm of these added cations. If Fe is present interference in analysis of Cu is observed. This latter interference can be cured by adding specific amount of H₃PO₄, to minimize almost all of it.

THE estimation of copper element is vitally important in many fields of natural science. Its determination in agricultural, metallurgical, geological and biological samples, by several methods are well established. Classical schemes use gravimetric, volumetric and electrodeposition procedures and instrumental techniques include spectrophotometry, optical emission spectroscopy, X-ray fluorescence, flame emission photometry and cathode ray polarograph.

The potential usefulness of atomic absorption for the analysis of metallic elements was first suggested in 1955 by Walsh² and by Alkemade and Mitatz³.

Since that time, methods for the determination of some 65 elements have been developed, and numerous commercial instruments designed specifically for this type of analysis have become available.

Slavin⁴ has commented that early workers have shown that the primary advantage of atomic absorption is its freedom from various analytical interferences, specially spectral interference. However, he has also mentioned that certain chemicals in solution, usually anions can prevent the release of a metal as an atomic vapour and thus causes an analytical error. Platte and Mary⁵ found no interference on 1 ppm copper by 1000 ppm of SO₄, Cl, PO₄, NO₃, NO₂ and HCO₃. Fishman and Downs⁶ reported that cations and anions normally found in natural waters do not interfere in the determination of copper. David⁷ reported a decrease in the absorbance when the sulphuric acid was added and attributed this change due to viscosity effect. Strastlein⁸ et al, found no interference on the copper analysis by 10,000 ppm Ca, Na, K or Co and 5,000 ppm Fe,

in H₂SO₄ or in HCl. However Kinson and Belcher⁹ reported no interference in HCl, HNO₃, H₂SO₄ and H₃PO₄.

It is obvious that the condition surrounding the copper while being determined using this method is very important. Interference can or cannot take place depending on many parameters. We feel that a wide range of conditions is in order to clarify the optimum situation of estimating copper accurately and at reasonable speed.

The present work deals with relatively more details than the previous studies. Instrumental as well as analytical conditions are investigated. The interference effect of large concentrations of HCl, HNO₃, H₂SO₄, HClO₄ and H₃PO₄ acids on the recovery of different concentrations of Cu ranging from 1 ppm to 20 ppm (per one ml) are investigated.

Also the effect of added cations Na, K, Cu, Fe, Al and Mg are being examined.

The data were obtained by measuring the absorbance of various solutions, each containing a different concentration of the interferent, and normalizing these absorbances against that of the solution containing no interferent.

All these measurements were carried out under various instrumental conditions, such as flame type and width, burner height for each flow rate.

Both the enhancement and the depression effect were recorded and projected on diagrams showing clearly the interference effect produced.

*To whom all correspondence should be addressed.

Experimental

Materials :

All chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade. JCl (sp. gr. 1.18), H_2SO_4 (sp. gr. 1.84), HNO_3 (sp. gr. 1.42), $HClO_4$ (sp. gr. 1.299) and H_3PO_4 (sp. gr. 1.70). Copper solutions were prepared by dissolving 1.0 g of copper metal in 50 ml of 6 n HNO_3 , cool and dilute to one liter. (1 ml = 1 mg Cu) This is our stock solution.

Instrumental :

Perkin-Elmer Model 303 atomic absorption spectrophotometer. The following conditions were used = burner bath length, 10 cm. Lamp current, 14 mA, from a copper hollow-cathode, lamp which was supplied by Perkin-Elmer Company. The wave length of absorption was 325.8. nm, slit width 4 nm, and air pressure 30 psi, acetylene pressure 8 psi. Acetylene flow was used to vary the type of the flame from optimum, 32 to oxidizing, 25 and reducing, 42 ; while keeping the air flow at 55 and having one slot burner. However, when 3 slot burner is used the acetylene flow varied from 36 (opt) to 32 (oxid) and 42 red., keeping the air flow at 60. Burner height was measured vertically in millimeters from the top of the burner to the center of the light beam at its point of focus. Two types of the burner, one slot and 3 slot, were used in the present study.

Results and Discussion

A thorough investigation, using the atomic absorption spectroscopy, to analyze the copper under a wide range of conditions is carried out. Effect of added mineral acids on the absorbance of Cu under various instrumental conditions is being examined and reported here. Having established the best conditions of analyzing Cu in acid media we then attempt to see the effect of added cations on the absorbance of Cu.

A. Effect of Acids

Three concentrations of Cu have been used, namely 1 ppm, 5 ppm and 20 ppm. In each case of these three concentration effect of added HCl, HNO_3 , H_2SO_4 , $HClO_4$ and H_3PO_4 acids on the absorbance of Cu is reported.

Five sets of sixteen solutions each were prepared. In each set five solutions containing 1 ppm Cu, five solutions 5 ppm Cu, five solutions containing 20 ppm Cu and the last one is the blank solutions. To each set of Cu concentration varying quantities of the acid under investigation were added ranging from zero to 50% by volume.

The absorbance of each of these solutions was read in three types of flame (optimum, oxidation and reducing), using two types of burner (one slot and three slot), and at two different burner heights (1 cm and 3 cm).

1. Effect of Hydrochloric Acid

With 3-slot burner head and 1 cm height the experiment show that there is enhancement effect at low concentration (1 ppm) using both oxidising and optimum flame conditions and suppression effect using reducing flame, while at higher concentration (5 ppm, 20 ppm) the effect of HCl becomes less serious, particularly using reducing and oxidizing flame conditions. With 3-slot burner head and 3 cm height, low concentration (1 ppm) of HCl show an enhancement effect using the optimum condition while with reducing flame there is no serious effect below 2% acid concentration. On the other hand, using oxidizing flame there is no effect below 4% acid concentration. At higher concentration of the acid the enhancement effect starts to be noticeable. Using one-slot burner head, low concentration (1 ppm) show suppression effect while at higher concentration and below 2% acid there is no significant interference.

From the above observations it is concluded that the best condition for copper estimation using hydrochloric acid is 3-slot burner head and 3 cm height using reducing flame and the concentration of acid must not exceed 8%, in order to minimize the possible interference of chloride ions.

2. Effect of HNO_3

Using 3-slot burner head, depression of absorbance is observed both at 1 cm and 3 cm height and with all types of flame. However using one-slot burner head and at 1 cm height, effect at low concentration of Cu with reducing and oxidizing flame is negligible up to 20% acid added. Under these latter conditions but higher Cu concentrations (5 and 20 ppm) depression in absorbance is observed under the three types of flames. At 3 cm height with one-slot burner no interference is observed at low concentration (1 ppm) in reduced flame and depression effect is observed at higher concentrations. With oxidizing and optimum flames the depression effect is clear at all concentrations. It is obvious that the best conditions for estimating Cu in HNO_3 is when one-slot burner head is used and 1 cm or 3 cm height using reducing flame or 1 cm height using oxidizing flame and the concentration of HNO_3 should not be more than 30%.

3. Effect of H_2SO_4

The experiment confirmed the interference of sulphate ion under all conditions and the suppression effect of added sulphuric acid.

4. Effect of $HClO_4$

With 3-slot burner head, a slight enhancement of absorption with increasing acid concentration and in optimum condition is observed both at 1 and 3 cm height. With reducing flame this enhancement levels at 4% $HClO_4$. With one-slot burner head and optimum as well as oxidizing flame condition seems

to produce no interference for copper absorption when the light beam passes the burner head at 1 cm height. At 1 cm level there is a slight decrease in absorption both with using optimum and reducing flames while using burner height of 3 cm.

Conclusively the best conditions of Cu determination in HClO_4 from the point of view of minimizing the possible interference is the one-slot

burner head at 1 cm height and using optimum flame.

5. Effect of H_3PO_4 :

Only the low concentration of Cu (1 ppm) when using 3 or one slot burner and 1 cm or 3 cm height flame and the three kind's of flame, show no interference of H_3PO_4 up to 15% acid concentration.

Fig. 1. Effect of added cations to Cu - H_3PO_4 mixture.

All other conditions show depression in the absorbance of Cu.

B. Effect of added Cations

For many useful industrial applications, copper is usually analyzed in presence of some other elements or cations.

As perchloric acid was found to have the minimum interference effect, when one-slot burner, 1 cm height and oxidizing flame is used. We carried out the determination of Cu using this above condition in presence of the cation K, Na, Ca, Mg, Al and Fe. All solutions were made in 8% HClO_4 and 5 ppm Cu except in case of K no acid was added due to precipitation. The concentrations of these cations varied in the range from 500 ppm to 10,000 ppm. Figure 1 shows the observed interfering effects. It can be seen that none of these cation affected the absorbance of Cu except for the case of Fe. Addition of Fe did enhance the absorbance. Therefore case should be taken whenever analysis of Cu in presence of Fe has to be done.

Due to this interfering effect, in case of Fe, we elaborated in that point little further. Additional experiments were carried out under various H_3PO_4 concentrations and no HClO_4 at all. It was found that the interfering effect disappeared when the concentration of Fe and H_3PO_4 were adjusted simultaneously. Table 1 shows this range of con-

centration at which no interference of Fe (in presence of H_3PO_4 on Cu was observed.

Conclusion

Our study, includes analysis of Cu in acidic media using atomic absorption spectroscopy. It is seen that the best acidic media is 2% HClO_4 , using one-slot burner head at 1 cm height of optimum flame. Analysis of Cu in presence of cations such as Na, K, Ca, Mg and Al up to 10,000 ppm showed no interference in HClO_4 media. However care must be taken when analysis of Cu has to be done in presence of Fe. This can be cured by adding specific amount of H_3PO_4 , as indicated in Table 1, which minimizes the interference greatly.

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TABLE 1—THE AMOUNT OF H_3PO_4 ACID WHICH MUST BE ADDED BEFORE THE MEASUREMENT IN PRESENCE OF DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS OF IRON IN THE MEASURED SOLUTION

Concentration of Fe (ppm)	Amount of H_3PO_4 % added
0—1000	8
1000—3500	10
3500—8500	20
8500—10,000	30%